

OpenWebSearch.EU

*Piloting a Cooperative Open Web Search
Infrastructure to Support Europe's Digital
Sovereignty*

***Deliverable D5.2 Training material
available for partners***

Version 1.0

Open Web Search

The Project is funded by the EC under GA 101070014

Funded by
the European Union

OPENWEBSEARCH.EU

1. Introduction7

2. Infrastructure Architecture Elements.....9

3. Technical workflows running on the OWS-FDI..... 15

4. Integration with the LEXIS Platform20

5. Interfaces.....22

6. Logging and Monitoring Service.....25

7. OWS Data Distribution Layer (OWS-DDL).....26

8. Security.....29

9. Conclusion.....33

Appendix.....34

Preliminaries

i. Project Info

Project number	101070014
Project acronym	OWS.eu
Project name	OpenWebSearch.eu – Piloting a Cooperative Open Web Search Infrastructure to Support Europe's Digital Sovereignty
Call	HORIZON-CL4-2021-HUMAN-01
Topic	HORIZON-CL4-2021-HUMAN-01-05
Type of action	HORIZON-RIA
Responsible unit	DG CNECT
Project starting date / Duration	01/09/2022 – 31/08/2025 (36 months)
Project reporting period	2
Project Coordinator	Prof. Dr. Michael Granitzer, University of Passau

ii. Project Partners

Acronym	Partner
UNI PASSAU	University of Passau
BADW-LRZ	Leibniz Supercomputing Centre of the Bavarian Academy of Sciences and Humanities
RU	Radboud University
WEBIS	Leipzig University
TUGraz	Graz University of Technology
DLR	German Aerospace Center
IT4I@VSB	Technical University of Ostrava
CERN	Organisation européenne pour la recherche nucléaire
OSF	Open Search Foundation e.V.
A1	A1 Slovenia
CSC	Tieteen tietotekniikan keskus Oy (IT Center for Science)
NLNET	Stichting NLnet
BUW	Bauhaus-Universität Weimar (Associated Partner)
SUMA-EV	SuMa e.V. - Verein für freien Wissenszugang (Associated Partner)

iii. Deliverable Info

Due Date / Delivery Date	30/09/2024 (M25)
Deliverable Lead	CERN
Deliverable type	Documentation
Dissemination level	PU
Document Status / Version	V1.0
Work-package / Lead Partner	WP5/CERN
Authors	<u>Noor Afshan Fathima</u> , <u>Andreas Wagner</u> , John Truckenbrodt, Mohamad Hayek, Martin Golasowski, Michael Dinzinger, Saber Zerhoud, Sebastian Schmidt, Ines Zelch, Gijs Hendriksen, Michael Granitzer
Approval	The deliverable expresses the opinion of the authors and has not yet been approved by the EC.
Related Publications	<p>“D 5.1 - Launch of the Pilot Infrastructure”¹. For an overview of the technical architecture of the federated data infrastructure.</p> <p>“D 1.1 - Crawler Coordination Software Stack & Demonstrator V1”². For an overview of the initial setup of the crawling system</p> <p>“D 1.2 – The OpenWebSearch Crawler and the Crawling Frontier Y2” For an overview of the current state of the crawling system</p> <p>“D 1.3 - Open Website Index & Open Crawl Storage Index v1” For an overview on the current state of the Open Website Index (OWI) and Open Crawl Storage Index (OCSI)</p> <p>“D 2.1 - The OpenWebSearch WARC Parsing & Content Analysis Library”³ For an updated overview of pre-processing and content analysis</p> <p>“D 3.3 - The OpenWebSearch Hub and the Open Web Index Y1”⁴. For an introductory overview on the OWSE-Hub and the index.</p> <p>“D 3.3 - The-OWI-And-OWSE-HUB-Y2” For an introductory overview on the OWSE-Hub and the index. Granitzer et al. for a high-level overview on the concept of the Open Web Index⁵</p> <p>Dinzinger et al. presenting preliminary results in setting up OWLer as Collaborative Web Crawler⁶</p>

¹ Deliverable D5.1 - Launch of the Pilot Infrastructure: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10838954>

² Deliverable D1.1 - The OpenWebSearch Crawler and the Crawling Frontier v1: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10355322>

³ Deliverable D2.1 - The OpenWebSearch WARC parsing & content analysis library Version 1.0:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10838722>

⁴ Deliverable D3.3 - The OpenWebSearch Hub and the Open Web Index: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10369512>

⁵ Granitzer, M., Voigt, S., Fathima, N. A., Golasowski, M., Guetl, C., Hecking, T., ... & Zerhoudi, S. (2023). Impact and development of an Open Web Index for open web search. *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*.

⁶ Dinzinger, M., Zerhoudi, S., Al-Maamari, M., Istaiti, M., Mitrovic, J. & Granitzer, M. (2023), OWLer: Preliminary results for building a Collaborative Open Web Crawler. *Open Search Symposium, Geneva*.

iv. Deliverable Summary

This document outlines the second deliverable of Work Package 5 (WP5) within the OpenWebSearch.eu project, titled "D5.2 Training Material for Partners." The project, funded by the European Commission under grant agreement GA 101070014 as part of the Horizon Europe Framework Program, aims to expand its federated data infrastructure through collaboration with two newly onboarded data centre infrastructure partners, selected via the 3rd FSTP call for proposals. These new partners join five existing federated data infrastructure partners to support the hosting and deployment of OWSAI technology.

This phase emphasizes developing and delivering comprehensive training materials for these partners, building on the progress made in the previous deliverable (D5.1 Launch of the Pilot Infrastructure). The document offers relevant statistics, links to existing documentation, and outlines a strategy for integrating technical documentation to ensure smooth and efficient onboarding and operations.

v. Document Management

History of Changes

Name	Version	Partner	Publication date	Changes
Initial Draft	0.1	CERN	July 2024	compose document
Version 1	0.2	CERN	September 2024	send for 1st review
Version 2	0.3	CERN	September 2024	Incorporated changes from review
Version 3	0.4	CERN	September 2024	Incorporate review changes for Security
Version 4	0.5	IT41	September 2024	Incorporate changes for OWS-DDL

vi. Document Approver(s) and Reviewer(s)

NOTE: All Approvers are required. Records of each approver must be maintained. All reviewers in the list are considered required unless explicitly listed as "Optional".

Name	Role	Action	Date
John Truckenbrodt	Contributor, reviewer	Initial review	20th September 2024
Mohamad Hayek	Contributor, reviewer	Initial review	23rd September 2024
Michael Granitzer	External reviewer	Review	25th September 2024
Andreas Wagner	WP5 Lead	Approved	25th September 2024
Michael Granitzer	Project Co-ordinator	Approved	30th September 2024

Executive Summary:

This deliverable presents the initial training materials designed to support newly onboarded infrastructure partners and serves as a valuable supplementary resource to the primary code repository hosted on a Gitlab⁷ instance and a central OWS Zenodo⁸ repository. These repositories house the essential documentation needed for partners to seamlessly integrate into the OpenWebSearch (OWS) infrastructure and serve as a foundation for the comprehensive training materials being developed.

The document provides an in-depth overview of the implementation, integration, and operational procedures of the OpenWebSearch Federated Data Infrastructure (OWS-FDI). It offers a comprehensive exploration of the OWS-FDI, detailing the vision and goals for onboarding new infrastructure partners and explaining the technical workflows that support the crawling, preprocessing, and indexing pipeline running within the OWS-FDI. Furthermore, it outlines the integration processes, the structure of the federated storage architecture, and the security measures that are essential for understanding and successfully onboarding partners into the OWS-FDI environment. This approach ensures that all aspects of the infrastructure are covered, providing a clear pathway for new partners to seamlessly integrate and contribute to the OWS-FDI.

In conclusion, this document offers insights into how we maintain a secure, transparent, and efficient data infrastructure that is adaptable and capable of supporting ongoing collaboration. It aims to empower our partners to effectively adopt, contribute to, and enhance the OWS-FDI as we continue to expand and evolve the data infrastructure together. For easy access, we provide links to the two central repositories where the source code and a comprehensive archive of documents can be found. As each component of the OWS-FDI is introduced, relevant links to their specific code and/or documentation will be shared accordingly. A summary of all these links can be found in Table 3, located in Appendix A.1, for quick reference and access to the resources.

Link to the central GitLab repository:

<https://opencode.it4i.eu/openwebsearcheu>

Link to the central Zenodo repository:

<https://zenodo.org/communities/owseu/records>

⁷ <https://about.gitlab.com/>

⁸ <https://zenodo.org/>

1. Introduction

As we enter the third year of the OpenWebSearch.eu (OWS) project, we would like to briefly revisit our vision of building the OWS technical data infrastructure - The OWS Federated Data Infrastructure (OWS-FDI). The last deliverable (D5.1 Launch of the Pilot Infrastructure) outlined our strategic approach, detailing the design, implementation, and operational status of the technical architecture, as well as the ongoing enhancements of the OWS-FDI, which serves as the foundation of OWS technical data infrastructure. The number of these services remain the same as in last deliverable with an addition of a few tools, and we are continuously striving to further scale the existing infrastructure rapidly.

The infrastructure partners are collectively responsible for providing and managing computing and storage resources, as well as monitoring their usage, which supports the pipeline operations. Some infrastructure partners offer access to traditional High-Performance Computing (HPC) resources, while others provide Infrastructure-as-a-Service (IaaS) cloud resources. The pilot implementation of the OWS-FDI leverages the convergence of HPC, cloud computing, and Big Data (in this case, crawled web data) through user-friendly interfaces to achieve its objective of delivering a cross-data centre infrastructure for building an Open Web Index (OWI). This infrastructure conceptually demonstrates how Europe's extensive HPC and cloud resources can be effectively combined with large-scale web data to support not only search functionality but also web data analysis, artificial intelligence, and more.

As such, WP5's efforts are inherently collaborative, working across multiple domains. The search applications built from the generated web indices, as well as datasets downloaded for training Large Language Models (LLMs), play a critical role in developing and validating the OWS-FDI for real-world applications.

The OpenWebSearch.eu Community Programme⁹ sought to onboard third-party computing and data centres to provide the necessary infrastructure for hosting parts of the Open Web Index (OWI) as a proof-of-concept for the extension of the developed technology and engage in discussions on creating a sustainable future infrastructure. Through the 3rd FSTP call for proposals¹⁰, we successfully selected two additional data centres in June 2024, with their onboarding initiating from September 2024.

This report presents the overview and links to documentation of our developed software artefacts in a structured format, serving as initial training material for the new partners. As this section serves as the introduction to the document, it began with an overview of the OpenWebSearch Federated Data Infrastructure (OWS-FDI). The vision and goals for successfully onboarding partners are detailed in Section 1.1. Section 2 provides an overview of the OWS-FDI itself, including the core infrastructure architecture elements, with specific focus on the Crawling, Pre-processing, and Index Generation Pipeline in Section 2.1, integration with the LEXIS Platform in Section 2.2, Interfaces in Section 2.3, and the Log aggregation pipeline in Section 2.4.

Section 3 discusses the technical workflows running on the OWS-FDI, covering the crawling process in Section 3.1, preprocessing and content analysis in Section 3.2, and the indexing process in Section 3.3. The integration with the LEXIS Platform is elaborated on in Section 4, with detailed insights into the Compute Workflow Orchestration Engine in Section 4.1 and the HPC Workflow App in Section 4.2.

The interfaces used within the OWS infrastructure are explained in Section 5, where the OWS Engine Hub is covered in Section 5.1, and the OWS Download tools are discussed in Section 5.2, including owilix

⁹ <https://openwebsearch.eu/community/>

¹⁰ <https://openwebsearch.eu/community/3rdparty-calls/call3/>

(Section 5.2.1) and py4lexis (Section 5.2.2). Section 6 outlines the Logs Aggregation pipeline implemented on the crawling infrastructure.

The OWS Data Distribution Layer is described in Section 7, which includes details on Integrated Rule-Oriented Data System (iRODS¹¹) Data Federation in Section 7.1, the iRODS Version and OpenID¹² integration in Section 7.2, and the integration of S3-compliant storage with iRODS in Section 7.3.

Security measures are comprehensively addressed in Section 8, where authentication and access control protocols are discussed in Section 8.1, network and port configuration details are provided in Section 8.2, and regular security audits and reviews are outlined in Section 8.3. The section also covers incident reporting (8.5), and takedown requests (8.6),

Finally, Section 9 provides a conclusion and outlook, summarizing the document's insights and future steps for the OWS-FDI. This report makes extensive references to the previous deliverable (D5.1) and other related deliverables where applicable. Please note that some deliverables mentioned here are not yet publicly available, and we advise checking the central OWS Zenodo¹³ repository for future updates.

It adheres to specific typographical conventions for Abbreviations¹⁴, Services¹⁵, Fundamental Concepts¹⁶, Technology/Framework/Tools/Applications¹⁷, enhancing clarity and conciseness throughout. Additionally, the semantics of the figures are briefly clarified in their respective sections, enabling readers to easily correlate the text with the relevant illustrations.

Link to the central Gitlab repository: <https://opencode.it4i.eu/openwebsearcheu>

Link to the central Zenodo Repository: <https://zenodo.org/communities/owseu/records>

1.1 Vision and Goals for the successful on-boarding of partners

The two third-party partners selected through the 3rd FSTP call for proposals are NORDLINK and Exaion European Infrastructure (EEI). NORDLINK, based in Germany, is an academic institution focused on establishing a Federated Open Web Search Data Centre in Northern Europe. EEI, a French industry/SME partner, brings expertise in infrastructure management through Exaion's European operations. Both partners play a crucial role in expanding the federated data infrastructure required to support the Open Web Search and Analysis Infrastructure (OWSAI), strengthening the project's capacity to scale and ensuring the efficient hosting of OWSAI technology across Europe.

As data centres focused on providing computing and storage solutions, the newly selected partners bring significant expertise in system administration, supported by robust security measures in place to ensure secure resource management. Their teams are well-prepared to deploy and maintain the services outlined by the project. It is our responsibility to ensure their smooth onboarding into the OWS technical ecosystem.

To support this process, we provide comprehensive training materials, including links to publicly

¹¹ iRODS Consortium. iRODS, <https://irods.org/> (Last Accessed, September 24th, 2024).

¹² <https://openid.net/>

¹³ Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/>

¹⁴ Abbreviations are introduced alongside their full forms on first occurrence and compiled in Table 1 in the Appendix (Appendix A.2). Subsequent occurrences use only the abbreviations. The abbreviations OWS.eu and OWS are used interchangeably.

¹⁵ Services in OWS-FDI are displayed in **bolded italics** and detailed individually in Section 3, usage e.g., **Crawling Queue** (Section 3.4: Crawling Queue). For repeated occurrences of service names, **bolded italics** are applied on the first occurrence or depending on the context.

¹⁶ Fundamental Concepts are marked in *italics*, such as **OpenSearch cluster**, *object store*, etc. Each italicized term is included in the Glossary table (Table 5) in the Appendix (A.3) with definitions. *Italics* are used on the first mention of repeated fundamental concepts.

¹⁷ Technology/Framework/Tools/Applications are identified in **bold**, like **OpenSearch**, etc. When mentioned multiple times, **bolds** are used only on the first instance. Additionally footnotes provide links to their official websites. Bold is used for highlighting sometimes other than this.

accessible code repositories and accompanying documentation. These resources ensure partners have the initial tools necessary to integrate effectively into the federated infrastructure. Throughout this process, we collaborate closely with each partner to resolve any technical challenges and ensure full compliance with the project's infrastructure requirements.

Since this is a pilot exercise for both the newly onboarded partners and us, we aim to further develop and refine the documentation alongside it as the project progresses. This iterative approach will allow us to tailor the technical and procedural documentation based on real-world feedback, addressing any gaps and continuously improving the resources provided. While much of the documentation and code is publicly accessible, some configurations and repositories are secured behind the Single Sign-On (SSO) systems of the data centres to comply with security policies. This ensures the protection of sensitive information and guarantees adherence to legal, ethical, and societal considerations. Our collaborative onboarding process not only facilitates technical integration but also supports the continuous enhancement of documentation and best practices for future partners. While the official documentations of the services covers all required setup details, in our internal documentations, we explicitly list any steps or configurations we have followed, even if they are standard. This ensures clarity and helps onboard partners more efficiently.

This documentation process aligns with and fulfils the ethical values outlined by the Ethical, Legal, and Societal Aspects (ELSA) compliance of the project. By ensuring comprehensive and transparent documentation, we not only uphold the principles of ethical responsibility but also contribute to building trust and accountability within the project. Furthermore, this practice enhances the sustainability dimension by creating a structured knowledge base that supports long-term usability, facilitates future onboarding, and ensures that the project's objectives are achieved in an ethically conscious and legally compliant manner.

2. Infrastructure Architecture Elements

Figure 11 illustrates the architecture of the OWS-FDI, which functions as a data processing and distribution system for distributed computing and storage resources. The architecture is organized into five main layers, based on the arrangement of high-level components, as follows:

- **Layer 1** which are all presented within green boxes are collectively referred to as **Interfaces**.
- **Layer 2**, depicted in a purple box, is dedicated to Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure layer, also known as the **AAI layer**.
- **Layer 3** includes the in **Crawling, Pre-processing, and Index Generation layer**, all of which are housed within orange boxes.
- **Layer 4**, shown in a bright yellow box, constitutes the **Compute Infrastructure layer** necessary for data processing tasks.
- **The Data Distribution Layer**, visualized in a cyan box (bottom most), handles the dissemination of data across the network.

Figure 1: Federated Data Infrastructure

In addition to these layers, the architecture includes the following supplementary components:

- *Single Sign-On (SSO)* feature, which integrates with nearly all components to streamline user authentication and system access, indicated with the blue hexagonal component in Figure 1.
- **Logs Aggregation and Monitoring Service** which overlays on most components.
- The two backend components **Crawling Queue** and **Compute Workflow Orchestration Engine**.

The detailed description of each component within the different layers, along with their implementation, deployment status, and roadmap, was originally presented in Section 1, Section 2, and Section 3 of Deliverable 5.1. In this deliverable, however, we will revisit each of these components with a different approach.

Instead of the previous layer-by-layer structure, this section will introduce the components in a more interconnected manner. We will start by describing the crawling, preprocessing, and indexing pipeline, followed by the integration with the LEXIS Platform. Next, we will discuss advancements made in the interface layer, introduce the aggregation pipeline, and finally cover the OWS Data Distribution Layer (OWS-DDL). This approach is intended to provide context and a more holistic view of how these components interact, enhancing the understanding of their roles and relationships. As we explore each aspect, we will indicate where they are further elaborated in the subsequent sections of this document.

2.1 Crawling, Pre-processing and Index Generation Pipeline

The most significant output of the OWS project is the **Open Web Index (OWI)**, which serves as the foundation for developing additional products. During the first year, our primary focus was on establishing and deploying a complete pipeline capable of crawling a portion of the web, pre-processing and indexing web content, and storing the resulting indexes in shared storage. Figure 2 illustrates the placement of the key components of the pipeline within the OWS-FDI, offering a foundational understanding of the pipeline's structure. This overview helps set the context for the more detailed explanations provided in Section 3.1, 3.2 and 3.3 respectively which covers the pipeline, and Section 9, where the **OWS-DDL** is further discussed.

This pipeline includes several key components working together to ensure smooth data processing all of which are highlighted in Figure 2. The crawling process begins with the **Open Web Crawler (OWLer) system**, consisting of the **Crawler** and the **Crawling Queue** components, responsible for collecting web data. The crawled data is then passed through the **Pre-processing** component, where it is cleaned and prepared for indexing. Following this, the **Index-generation** component processes the data to create an index, which is then stored in the **OWS Data Distribution Layer (OWS-DDL)**, a shared storage layer that utilizes technologies such as **iRODS** and **EUDAT-B2SAFE**¹⁸ to ensure data management and accessibility.

Figure 2: Primary pipeline

¹⁸ <https://www.eudat.eu/b2safe>

2.2 Integration with the LEXIS Platform:

In the second year, we refined and enhanced this pipeline, making it more robust and incorporating it into the LEXIS Platform. As depicted in Figure 1, the highlighted **Compute Workflow Orchestration Engine** and the **HPC Workflow App** represent key components of this integration with the LEXIS Platform. Additional details of these components are described in Section 4.

This integration included the introduction of an initial **Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (AAI)** Service, also highlighted in Figure 3, The LEXIS framework's AAI is leveraged for this purpose. Access to all platform services, independent of geographical location, is enabled via SSO through **Keycloak**¹⁹, the offered *Identity and Access Management (IAM)* solution. Keycloak operates uniquely yet cooperatively with B2Access²⁰, which is included as an IdP within Keycloak. This integration eliminates redundant logins, bolsters security by reducing credential duplication, and simplifies the user experience. It utilizes *OIDC*, *REST interfaces*, and *JWT tokens*²¹ for service interactions. Access control is managed by *role-based* or *attribute-based* mechanisms (RBAC/ABAC), with Keycloak handling the front-end of authentication, credential management, and session handling. The distributed nature of AAI augments system resilience. HEAppE middleware interfaces with local HPC centre's AAI solutions, providing a crucial integration and separation layer. We recommend consulting Section 2.3 of the D 5.1 for a detailed description.

Additionally, B2Access is the solution that provides the Single Sign On (SSO) mechanism via multiple authentication options like eduGAIN²² and ORCID²³. B2ACCESS authentication as highlighted in Figure 3, is the primary login gateway, positioned at the forefront of both internal facing interface components such as the **HPC Workflow App** and public facing interface components like OpenWebSearch Engine Hub (**OWSE-Hub**) which we will briefly describe next.

Figure 3: Primary pipeline integrated with the LEXIS framework components

¹⁹ Keycloak: <https://www.keycloak.org/>

²⁰ <https://eudat.eu/service-catalogue/b2access>

²¹ JSON Web Tokens: <https://jwt.io/>

²² <https://edugain.org/>

²³ <https://orcid.org/>

2.3 Interfaces:

In addition to the OWI, another key output of the project is the **OWSE-Hub**, which is currently in continuous development and will soon be deployed. The development of the **OWSE-Hub** began in the first year as we successfully started gathering data and transforming it into a usable index. As part of this effort, we developed a user interface around **MOSAIC** (the search application software developed in the project, highlighted as "**WebSearch Applications**" in Figure 4) to enable the easy setup and deployment of custom search engines on top of the OWI. In Figure 4, the **OWS-Engine Hub** represents this user interface component.

To further facilitate the use of the OWI, we focused on developing a command-line tool named **OWLix** in the second year. This tool allows users to efficiently filter and access parts of the index for downloading or remote querying. The **OWS Download** component shown in Figure 4 consists of the OWLix tool in addition to **Py4Lexis**, both of which are further detailed under Section 5.

The Interface Layer **Custom UIs** highlighted in Figure 4 includes specialized applications, such as **Web Analytic Applications**, that utilize the provided web data. Our goal is to support a broad spectrum of use cases beyond search, accommodating various technological setups and requirements. A key aspect for any Custom UI application is ensuring proper authentication, either for the application itself or for its users, to gain authorized data access. This data access is facilitated in one of two ways: either through direct download via the **HPC Workflow App** introduced in Section 2.2, or through offloading via the **OWS Observability & Control App**, which will be discussed in the following sub-section.

Both data provisioning facilities depend on the underlying access layers, the **OWS Observability & Control App** as well as the **HPC Workflow App**.

Figure 4: Interfaces

2.4 Log Aggregation and Monitoring Service:

In addition to these components there is an aggregation pipeline that processes the logs generated by the **OWLer** system. These logs are crucial for gaining insights into the behaviour of crawlers and the dynamics of the web pages they visit. The **Logs Aggregation and Monitoring Service** component in Figure 5 serves this purpose. The main objective of this pipeline is to convert raw crawler log data into meaningful, aggregated data sets, enabling efficient querying and analysis. This component is elaborated in Section 6.

After completing the initial phase of running the Logs Aggregation Pipeline and gathering data, we proceeded to prototype the public dashboard featured within the **OWS Observability & Control App**, as depicted in Figure 5, which also makes the OWI accessible to users. This dashboard among other things offers a detailed view of system performance and relevant statistics derived from the log aggregation pipeline. Its architecture is designed for distributed operation, ensuring scalable monitoring across the entire infrastructure. Detailed explanation of this component can be found in D 1.3.

Figure 5: Log Aggregation and Monitoring

3. Technical workflows running on the OWS-FDI

In the previous section, we provided a high-level introduction to each component of the OWS-FDI, outlining their overall purpose within the infrastructure. From this section onwards this section, we will delve deeper into the technical workflows operating within the OWS-FDI most relevant to the infrastructure partners. As mentioned earlier, our primary focus in the initial years of the project was to develop and deploy a comprehensive pipeline that could crawl segments of the web, preprocess and index the web content, and store the resulting indexes in shared storage for easy access and further analysis. This approach ensures that the OWS-FDI can efficiently process and manage web data, contributing to the broader objectives of the OpenWebSearch initiative.

Figure 6: Cluster tiers in the core architecture behind the OWI. A cluster tier is defined as a set of machines running a well-defined software stack in the same physical data-centre for a particular purpose with clear, well defined interfaces to other cluster tiers

We describe the different cluster tiers in more detail in the below sub-sections.

3.1 Crawling

Crawling takes place on the following two cluster tiers:

- The Crawling Cluster Tier (CCT) contains a crawler responsible for crawling the Web, thereby creating WARC files (i.e., collections of HTTP streams from the crawling process). These WARC²⁴ files are stored in an S3 bucket²⁵ that can be accessed by the other tiers. There can be multiple CCT, but there should be only one CCT per data centre, as the CCT can scale with the amount of resources provided.
- The Crawler Frontier Tier (CFT) is a singleton tier (i.e., only one instance exists across all participating data centres). It coordinates the multi-tier crawling process, keeping track of crawled URLs, access statistics and cache digest. The crawler frontier is the primary data source for the website registry, which provides the interface for interaction between webmasters and the frontier (e.g., an interface for take-down requests).

The CCT consists of the **OWLER (OWS crawler)**, a distributed web crawler built with StormCrawler²⁶ running on Apache Storm²⁷, at each individual data centre. Aside from regular crawling functionality, the OWLER also includes a classifier for distinguishing between benign, malicious and adult content.

The CFT consists of a single OpenSearch²⁸ instance running at one of the data centres. It also contains a metrics server which aggregates logs from different stages and allows for (limited) statistical analysis.

Currently (September 2024), the CCT has been deployed successfully at five partner sites (UNI PASSAU, BADW-LRZ, IT4I@VSB, CSC and DLR) and is in operation at three (BADW-LRZ, IT4I@VSB and CSC). The CFT is deployed at CERN. At peak operating time, the CCT crawls roughly 1TB of content per day per data centre, but can theoretically be scaled up by using more machines. This requires also to resolve security related issues, like raising false positive network security alarms when accessing botnets. However, the frontier still remains a bottleneck to be scaled up accordingly with the number of machines used.

Detailed descriptions of the OWLER components, as depicted in Figure 1, can be found in Section 2.4 of D5.1. The most recent updates on the crawling system are documented in Deliverable D1.2 – The OpenWebSearch Crawler and the Crawling Frontier Y2. The new data centre partners have the potential to contribute to this system by offering Virtual Machines (VMs) for deployment of this system, while also ensuring that the necessary security measures are in place to maintain data integrity and compliance across the federated infrastructure.

Since August 2023, OWLER has conducted around 10.76B fetches (general-purpose crawling without complementary crawls). These web page visits were conducted on over different 40.5M hosts (Table 1). This is a remarkable number, despite the estimated number of around 193.5M active websites²⁹ (a website might be hosted across several hosts), as the frequency of visits is approximately following a Pareto distribution, with a few platforms getting the most of it.

²⁴ International Organization for Standardization. (2017). *Information and documentation – WARC file format* (ISO/DIS Standard No. 28500). Retrieved from <https://www.iso.org/standard/68004.html> (Last Accessed, September 24th, 2024).

²⁵ Amazon AWS S3. Available: <https://aws.amazon.com/s3/> (Last Accessed, September 24th, 2024).

²⁶ DigitalPebble, Ltd. (2014). StormCrawler, <https://stormcrawler.apache.org/> (Last Accessed, September 24th, 2024).

²⁷ <https://storm.apache.org/>

²⁸ Amazon Web Services (2021). OpenSearch, <https://opensearch.org/> (Last Accessed, September 24th, 2024).

²⁹ <https://sitefy.com/how-many-websites-are-there/>

Table 1: Statistics on General-Purpose crawling (since August 2023) - Status August 2024

Visited URLs (per day)³⁰	Up to ~105M / day
Visited URLs (total)	10,757,755,422 until 6 th of August 2024
Unique visited URLs	1,170,925,504 until 6 th of May 2024
Unique visited hosts	40,531,574 until 6 th of May 2024
Number of unique languages	184
Volume of created WARC files	315 TB since October 2023

Zenodo Repo OWLer StormCrawler (for the source code described in this deliverable):

<https://zenodo.org/records/13836849>

Source Code OWLer StormCrawler (including further development changes from the Zenodo Repo):

<https://opencode.it4i.eu/openwebsearcheu-public/owler>

Zenodo Repo OWLer URL Frontier (for the source code described in this deliverable):

<https://zenodo.org/records/13836904>

Source Code OWLer URL Frontier (including further development changes from the Zenodo Repo):

<https://opencode.it4i.eu/openwebsearcheu-public/urlfrontier>

Source Code OWLer Installation Toolkit (including scripts to set up the OWLer system):

<https://opencode.it4i.eu/openwebsearcheu-public/owler-installation-toolkit>

Source Code OWLer Log Aggregation (including the Apache Flink topology and installation scripts):

<https://opencode.it4i.eu/openwebsearcheu-public/log-aggregation>

Source Code Crawler Evaluator (including scripts to benchmark OWLer StormCrawler):

<https://opencode.it4i.eu/openwebsearcheu-public/owler-crawler-benchmark>

Documentation:

<https://openwebsearcheu.pages.it4i.eu/wp1/owseu-crawler/owler/>

³⁰ Note that this number has been achieved during a test crawl spanning 20 days (20.06.2024 - 11.07.2024).

3.2 Preprocessing and content analysis

Preprocessing and content analysis encompasses the following two cluster tiers:

- The Preprocessing and Enrichment Tier (PET) takes the WARC files from the S3 Bucket filled by the CCT and extracts cleaned HTML and metadata. The extracted metadata includes the page's language, several properties derived from the URL, and Curlie³¹ topics. Later on, other metadata such as geo-information and entities will also be extracted. Following the partitioning of the CCT, each data centre should have a dedicated PET for the WARC files stored at that data centre. The metadata extracted by the PET is stored in Parquet format.
- The Preprocessing Plugins Evaluation Tier (PPET) is another singleton tier that enables the evaluation of plugins for the content analysis library. In order to expand enrichment capabilities, both project members as well as third parties may develop plugins to be used in the PET.

To ensure good quality and sufficient throughput, candidate plugins first have to perform their enrichment task on problem-specific benchmarking data (e.g., a classification dataset for a plugin performing webpage classification), using an instance of the TIRA³² platform hosted at one of the data centres. This platform provides the means for evaluation as a service with a focus on information retrieval research. It can host shared tasks on a given research problem, run submitted software in virtual machines and thereby create reproducible results.

The PET uses Apache Spark batch jobs that apply Resiliparse³³ to parse and clean the HTML content and apply several types of metadata enrichment. The work on this tier is outlined in further detail in Deliverable D2.1.

The PET runs currently (September 2024) at the same infrastructure sites as the CCT (BADW-LRZ, IT4I@VSB and CSC). Functionality is in place to estimate the amount of resources required for processing a day's worth of WARC files, such that the PET can scale along with the amount of content being crawled by the CCT.

The PPET builds upon TIRA, a platform for replicability and comparison of information retrieval experiments. Currently, TIRA is hosted at WEBIS and is being used for the evaluation of several shared tasks at well-known IR conferences. We are looking into hosting a TIRA instance at one of the infrastructure partners, to serve as the core part of the PPET to evaluate PET plugins.

Link to source code of Resiliparse:

<https://github.com/chatnoir-eu/chatnoir-resiliparse>

Link to source code of Resilipipe:

<https://opencode.it4i.eu/openwebsearcheu-public/preprocessing-pipeline>

³¹ Curlie. Available: <https://curlie.org/> (Last Accessed, September 24th, 2024).

³² Fröbe, Maik, et al. "Continuous integration for reproducible shared tasks with TIRA.io." *European Conference on Information Retrieval*. Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland, 2023.

³³ Bevendorff, Janek, et al. "Elastic chatnoir: Search engine for the clueweb and the common crawl." *Advances in Information Retrieval: 40th European Conference on IR Research, ECIR 2018, Grenoble, France, March 26-29, 2018, Proceedings 40*. Springer International Publishing, 2018.

3.3 Indexing

Indexing is supported in the Index and Storage Tier (IST).

The IST turns the cleaned content from the PET into a usable index/inverted file. Similar to the CCT and the PET, each data centre should have its own IST (and only one), responsible for creating an index for the documents crawled by that data centre. Indexes are inverted files partitioned into so-called “shards” by selected types of metadata derived by the PET (e.g., topic and language), distributed as CIFF³⁴ files.

Similar to the PET, the IST is implemented as a Spark batch job. In its current state, it reads the Parquet files delivered by the PET and writes out inverted files per shard (by arbitrary metadata values). This allows us to build semantically coherent shards of the full web index (dependent on the metadata extracted by the PET), which can be used to enable a large variety of downstream search engines. For instance, language can be used to build search engines for specific countries, geo-information can be used to focus on specific areas, and classified topics or genres can be used to build search engines focusing on a specific area (like news and/or sports).

Aside from creating the CIFF files per shard, the IST also copies the Parquet files written by the PET and partitions them alongside the CIFF files. The Parquet files are distributed alongside the CIFF files and can be used to enrich the index with the appropriate metadata.

Currently (September, 2024) the IST has successfully been deployed to BADW-LRZ, IT4I@VSB and CSC. Current efforts are focusing on more robust deployment of the PET and IST, and making this process more automated. Future work in this task needs to resolve the questions that arise from a fully evolving index; for example, how and if CIFF files should be updated in response to changing document content and/or take-down requests.

Link to source code of Spark Indexer :

<https://opencode.it4i.eu/openwebsearcheu-public/spark-indexer>

Spark deployment framework :

<https://opencode.it4i.eu/openwebsearcheu-public/spark-indexer>

³⁴ Lin, Jimmy, et al. "Supporting Interoperability Between Open-Source Search Engines with the Common Index File Format". *Proceedings of the 43rd International ACM SIGIR Conference on Research and Development in Information Retrieval*. 2020.

4. Integration with the LEXIS Platform

Elaborating on the components introduced in Section 2.2, we now further dwell into the part where our pipeline was enhanced to make it more robust and incorporated into the LEXIS Platform also extending its operation to an additional HPC data centre.

4.1 Compute Workflow Orchestration Engine

The Compute Workflow Orchestration Engine component is the backend of the **HPC Workflow App** as depicted in Figure 11, it streamlines HPC workflows and jobs for the development of the OWI from crawled data, utilizing pre-processing and indexing jobs. We re-visit the description of this component also found in Section 2.2 of D5.1 under the same heading. Initially, OWS utilized traditional *batch scheduling* systems for resource allocation based on *cluster* priorities. Access to these processes was primarily through SSH, connecting to a frontend node of an HPC cluster, with operations conducted via a *Command Line Interface (CLI)*. The transition towards the automated system took place by utilizing the **Compute workflow orchestration engine**, a component of the LEXIS³⁵ Platform. It handles the challenges of OWS-FDI's heterogeneity, scale, and geographic distribution. It also interacts efficiently with the batch scheduler, meeting high-level objectives. Therefore, leveraging the advanced execution environment provided by HPC partners within the LEXIS framework, which offers access to supercomputers and cloud resources. This integration significantly enhances the handling and transfer of large data volumes, particularly in connection with OWS-DDL.

This component offers developers developing the pre-processing and index generation components to define workflows utilizing the **HPC Workflow App** as the frontend interface, specify execution resources, and ensure seamless integration with **AAI** for security. The management of data, when the crawled data is located differently from computation sites, is also taken care of by interfacing with the OWS-DDL. It abstracts out and manages software provisioning, creation of *virtual machines (VMs)*, *container* uploads, and task assignment across the computing infrastructure (Layer 4). It defines input data, output locations, and processing steps, ensuring efficient task distribution. It collaborates with **HEAppE**³⁶ *middleware* to provide secure access to HPC/cloud infrastructures.

We are in the process of evaluating and strategizing how to effectively integrate the computing and storage resources of the newly onboarded partners with the existing infrastructure currently running these workflows and jobs. To evaluate and support this integration, a detailed online training program is being planned in the month of October 2024, which will offer comprehensive and in-depth live training for seamless integration into the workflow orchestration engine.

Link to Public Documentation: <https://opencode.it4i.eu/lexis-platform>

³⁵ LEXIS Platform Documentation: <https://docs.lexis.tech/>

³⁶ High-End Application Execution Middleware (HEAppE): <https://heappe.eu/>

4.2 HPC Workflow App

The HPC Workflow App component as depicted in Figure 1 provides a user-friendly web interface that centralizes resource allocations across multiple clusters. It enables users to launch a pipeline with a single click, access logs, manage data through iRODS³⁷, and utilizes a unified web login for seamless access and control as depicted in Figure 3 showing a glimpse of the interface and the crawling system. The detailed description of this component can be found in Section 2.2 of D5.1 under the same heading. To access this interface first a LEXIS account needs to be created³⁸. Once a LEXIS account has been created, access to the LEXIS OpenWebSearch project has to be granted. For this, an E-mail can be written to support@lexis.tech.

Figure 7: Publicly available datasets for download via the HPC Workflow App

In the **HPC Workflow App**, the pre-processing and indexing tasks initiate new workflow executions that trigger the corresponding scripts. List of the workflows running in the LEXIS Platform is visible in 7. These processes are organized and visualized as DAGs, as seen in Figure 8. For both the workflows, a Apache Spark cluster is configured and deployed within the HPC environment. A Spark job is then submitted to this cluster to index preprocessed data for a specified day (as specified in LEXIS).

Link to Public Documentation: <https://docs.lexis.tech>

³⁷ Integrated Rule-Oriented Data System (iRODS): <https://irods.org/>

³⁸ LEXIS Platform web GUI: <https://portal.lexis.tech>

Figure 8: Workflow execution organized and displayed as Directed Acyclic Graphs (DAGs)

5. Interfaces

Elaborating on the components introduced in Section 2.3, we now further dwell into the part where our interfaces are further extended with improvements to the old ones and addition of the new.

5.1 OWS Engine Hub

The OWS project yields two significant products: The OWI and the **OWSE-HUB**. The OWSE-HUB is envisioned as a platform akin to **Docker Hub**³⁹, but in the context of search engines. It is envisioned as web-based Graphical User Interface (GUI) system that provides a suite of comprehensive search engine stacks. This setup is intended to facilitate the rapid and efficient development of new search verticals. The groundwork for this system will be laid by the partners responsible for establishing the necessary infrastructure. In collaboration with the researchers and developers who take the lead in the actual development of the OWSE-HUB. It is envisioned to access the OWS-DDL, from where pulling of the *index* with specifications would be facilitated. The overall concept and system architecture of the software developed following the vision of OWSE-HUB is called MOSAIC2go⁴⁰ which enables users to create and configure a search engine that uses datasets downloaded from the OWI. The detailed description of concepts and system architecture can be found in D3.3.

The setup described in D3.3 serves as an example for deploying MOSAIC2go on any private cloud infrastructure (eg **OpenStack**). Depending on the IaaS platform the partner is using, it can adapt this design to fit the specific services, tools, and configurations offered by their chosen platform. The key components and considerations remain consistent, but the implementation details may vary based on the capabilities and features provided by the IaaS environment.

³⁹ <https://hub.docker.com/>

⁴⁰ <https://zenodo.org/records/13800054>

Link to source code of MOSAIC2go (Private and password protected repositories):

<https://opencode.it4i.eu/openwebsearcheu/wp4/mosaic2go-configuration-service>

<https://opencode.it4i.eu/openwebsearcheu/wp4/mosaic2go-web-frontend>

5.2 OWS Download

The OWS Download component as depicted in Figure 1 provides end users with streamlined access to vital datasets produced as the end result of pre-processing and indexing workflows. The download feature, accessible through the HPC Workflow App (Section 4.2), enables users to effortlessly download datasets. We here briefly present the two download tools - `owlix` and `py4Lexis` as shown in Figure 3, which we briefly describe and provide documentation to. Although not strictly required to enter the federation, we ask the new partners to install, test them in-order to enhance their data management capabilities.

Figure 9: OWS Download

5.2.1 owilix

The **owilix** tool as depicted in Figure 9 is a sub component of OWS Download. It is being developed as user-friendly git-like command line interface for pushing, pulling and querying OWS data.

The Open Web Index Command Line Tool, owilix, has been developed to enhance access to the OWI. Designed for researchers, developers, and data scientists, owilix facilitates the management and querying of web-scale datasets. It supports both pull (retrieval of OWI-shards) and push (community contributions) functionalities, with advanced SQL querying powered by DuckDB⁴¹ and Parquet format. owilix manages both local and remote datasets efficiently, ensuring seamless data handling. Its architecture integrates with the broader OWI ecosystem using iRODS for parallel downloads and py4lexis for general data access. Core features include a user-friendly CLI interface, version control, and secure authentication. Practical applications range from dataset querying and management to debugging data pipelines. This tool significantly contributes to open web search initiatives, providing powerful data management capabilities across diverse environments.

owilix lets you query OWI data based on metadata registered in either iRODS or in ancillary parquet files. For the latter, DuckDB SQL queries are used. Once the dataset of interest is located, py4lexis is utilised to communicate with the LEXIS Platform. LEXIS as stated earlier acts as central orchestrator for data management, abstracting the details of multiple federated storage locations. py4lexis will locate the dataset in the LEXIS infrastructure and prepare it for download including staging and compression. The actual storage, retrieval and transfer across the distributed system is managed by iRODS, including replication and mirroring. py4lexis will query iRODS to transfer the data to your machine while py4lexis may manage parallel downloads and compression tasks. All transfers will be logged in iRODS.

Installation instructions can be found in the README file of the owilix repository⁴². During execution, a browser window will be opened for authenticating with LEXIS. The generated token is valid for five days.

For a detailed architectural description referring to the Deliverable D3.3 is recommended.

Tutorial on using owilix:

https://openwebsearcheu-public.pages.it4i.eu/ows-the-book/content/howto/data_download_with_owilix.html

Tutorial on data slicing with owilix:

https://openwebsearcheu-public.pages.it4i.eu/ows-the-book/content/howto/data_slicing_with_owilix.html

⁴¹ <https://duckdb.org/>

⁴² <https://opencode.it4i.eu/openwebsearcheu-public/owi-cli>

5.2.2 py4lexis

The Py4Lexis tool is a Python package (compatible with versions 3.10 and 3.11) developed to provide a user-friendly manager for handling datasets within the OWS-DDL.

py4lexis is client library designed to interact with the LEXIS Platform, which is a distributed data and computational infrastructure. It provides functionality for managing large datasets, including operations like data upload, staging, compression, encryption, and metadata management. py4lexis enables users to automate the handling of distributed datasets across various storage nodes by abstracting complex orchestration tasks. It interfaces with storage systems such as iRODS to ensure efficient data transfer, secure access, and workflow automation within high-performance computing and data management environments.

To begin using Py4Lexis, users must log in via the LEXIS login page, where B2Access⁴³ credentials can be utilized for authentication. This ensures secure access to the OWS-DDL. For a more detailed understanding of OWS-DDL, please refer to Section 2.5 under the same heading of the D5.1 document.

Detailed usage instructions can be found on the LEXIS Platform Documentation page:

https://docs.lexis.tech/_pages/user_interfaces/py4lexis.html

6. Logging and Monitoring Service

The aggregation pipeline is responsible for processing the logs generated by the OWLer web crawlers. These logs provide valuable insights into crawler behaviour and the dynamics of the web pages they visit. Due to the substantial volume of data generated by these crawlers, aggregating this information is essential to ensure that it remains manageable and analysable. This aggregation process not only reduces the overall data size but also improves query performance, enabling faster and more efficient data retrieval. This component is deployed on cloud infrastructure at one of the data centres.

Detailed descriptions of the Logging and Monitoring Service, as illustrated in Figure 1, are available in Section 2.5 of D5.1. The latest updates on this system can be found in Deliverable D1.4 – The OpenWebSearch Index v1.

Source Code OWLer Log Aggregation (including the Apache Flink topology and installation scripts):

<https://opencode.it4i.eu/openwebsearcheu-public/log-aggregation>.

Documentation: <https://openwebsearcheu.pages.it4i.eu/wp1/owseu-crawler/owl/>

⁴³ <https://eudat.eu/service-catalogue/b2access>

7. OWS Data Distribution Layer (OWS-DDL)

We envisage the newly on-boarded partners to begin by federating their storage devices with the OWS Data Distribution Layer (OWS-DDL) which is illustrated in Figure 10. The detail description of which can be found in Section 2.5 of D5.1 This is a critical step, as integrating their storage systems into the OWS-DDL will enable seamless data distribution across the federated infrastructure. By federating their storage, they contribute as partners who will contribute to a decentralized and scalable network that ensures data availability, redundancy, and efficient management across the OWS ecosystem.

Figure 10 OWS Data Distribution Layer

Figure 11 Integration components of the OWS-DDL

There are two storage services used by the OWS as shown on Figure 11. The Integrated Rule-Oriented Data System (iRODS) is a well-established distributed data management solution and within OWS it is used as abstraction of local (typically POSIX) storage arrays, which enables federated data transfer between other connected locations. S3 protocol is used by the crawlers and processing pipelines to store the intermediate products such as raw WARC files. If there is a local S3-compatible service available, the processing pipelines can use it. Second option is to deploy local MinIO instance to provide fast S3 access to processing pipelines executed locally.

This process is essential to support the OWI, as it allows data to be stored and retrieved across multiple locations while maintaining consistency and security. This is achieved by the partners deploying the iRODS and providing access to the local S3 endpoint or deploying local MinIO instance.

7.1 iRODS Data Federation

iRODS is an open-source data management software used to organize, share, and secure large-scale, distributed data collections. It virtualises data storage, enabling organizations to manage data across heterogeneous storage systems while presenting users with a unified view of their data, irrespective of its physical location. iRODS implements a rule engine that allows organizations to automate data workflows and apply specific policies, such as data retention, replication, or access control, triggered by events like data creation or modification. This rule-based system offers flexible and customizable management, making iRODS suitable for scientific, governmental, and commercial environments where data integrity, provenance, and policy enforcement are critical.

iRODS also excels in metadata management by maintaining a catalogue of metadata for every file, dataset, or storage resource it manages. This makes it easy to search for and retrieve data based on attributes like content, owner, or creation time. The system supports secure collaboration by enabling users to access data across distributed environments through federated zones, allowing seamless sharing of data without physically moving it between storage systems. iRODS integrates with a wide array of storage technologies, and supports advanced features like data tiering to optimize storage utilization, automated indexing, and provenance tracking to ensure accountability and compliance. Its flexibility, scalability, and rich feature set make iRODS a powerful tool for managing complex data infrastructures

We utilize iRODS for data federation, allowing seamless management of distributed data across multiple zones. The federation configuration strictly adheres to the standard process as described in the iRODS documentation, with no special modifications applied. For our system, we use iRODS version 4.2.12⁴⁴ with upgrade to 4.3.x being planned as well.

Link to iRODS documentaion

<https://irods.org/documentation/>

Link to detailed iRODS installation:

https://docs.irods.org/4.2.12/getting_started/installation/

Link to detailed federation instructions:

https://docs.irods.org/4.2.12/system_overview/federation

Link to further reading:

https://irods.org/uploads/2021/Golasowski-Hayek-Ostrava-Leibniz-Transnational_Data_System_for_HPC_Cloud_Computing_Workflows_based_on_iRODS_EUDAT-paper.pdf

7.2 iRODS Version and OpenID Integration

The iRODS version 4.2.12, includes integration with the iRODS OpenID plugin. This plugin enables authentication using JWT (Jason Web Token) tokens, removing the need for traditional password-based authentication. The OpenID plugin allows seamless integration with the LEXIS Platform, leveraging token-based authentication to enhance security and streamline the process for users.

⁴⁴ <https://irods.org/>

Key Details

- **iRODS Version:** 4.2.12
- Link to the **OpenID Plugin** used for JWT token authentication:
https://github.com/lexis-project/irods_auth_plugin_openid.
- **Authentication Setup:** The plugin is installed on the iRODS server, enabling users to authenticate with tokens provided by the LEXIS Platform's token service.
- **Configuration File:** The `server_config.json` is configured to include the necessary token service details.

7.3 S3 and iRODS Integration

Crawler, indexing and postprocessing pipelines are based on Apache Spark which has a native integration with S3 compatible storages. We provide options to either use local S3-capable storage array or a local MinIO instance. After storing the data in S3, the data are processed by the pipelines and the result is published through the LEXIS Platform using the local iRODS zone.

The S3 storage is used only as a temporary buffer and the data are removed after certain amount of time. For local S3 instance, single service account with access and secret key is preferred due to variations in the access level control handling in various vendor-specific S3 implementations. For MinIO installation and configuration, referring to the official documentation is recommended.

Link to the official MinIO documentation:

<https://min.io/docs/minio/linux/operations/installation.html>

Summary of Integration

- **MinIO Usage:** MinIO is employed as temporary storage for WARC data, which is later transferred to iRODS.
- **iRODS OpenID Authentication:** Provides a secure, token-based authentication system that integrates with the broader LEXIS Platform for enhanced security and flexibility.

This integration ensures that our system can manage secure, federated access to distributed storage while maintaining the flexibility to work with third-party platforms.

8. Security

Security is managed by the respective Cloud/HPC's internal security departments. All the services running in the infrastructure and the access to the infrastructure resources itself are currently secured via IP address and thus not accessible from outside the participating services or computing centres. We expect the new partners to implement similar security measures, ensuring that access to their infrastructure is tightly controlled and conforms to the overall security standards of the federation. This includes implementing IP whitelisting, firewall rules, and network segmentation to prevent unauthorized access, as well as aligning with the best practices for managing data security and access control within the federated infrastructure. Partners are also encouraged to coordinate with their internal security teams to ensure continuous monitoring, regular audits, and adherence to legal, ethical, and compliance requirements in line with the project's broader objectives.

In Section 8.1, we will focus on explaining the various measures we've implemented to ensure that our systems are not only technically secure but also compliant with legal, ethical, and regulatory standards. We cover the measures we've implemented to ensure the security and integrity of our infrastructure, detailing how we follow best practices to safeguard our systems.

In Section 8.2, we outline the processes and actions we take to maintain a secure, compliant, and transparent environment for our data infrastructure. Specifically, we will describe our procedures for incident reporting, the actions taken in response to reported incidents and our approach to handling takedown requests.

These practices are designed to enable us to respond promptly and effectively to security threats, handle content removal requests responsibly, and maintain clear communication about data sharing and usage within our network. These measures are also highlighted in Section 4 of Deliverable 1.2

8.1 Authentication and Access Control

IP Whitelisting: We implement IP whitelisting in our firewall settings to allow only the IP addresses or ranges used by authorized services connecting from our partner data centres. This ensures that only pre-approved partners have access to the services, whether operating individually or within a federated environment as depicted in Figure 1 effectively preventing unauthorized access.

For instance, when crawlers running across multiple partner data centres need to connect to an external service, such as the Frontier service hosted at one specific data centre, we whitelist the IP addresses or ranges associated with those crawlers. This targeted approach ensures that only the designated crawlers operating at our partner locations can establish a connection, thereby enhancing the security, integrity, and control of the communication across our federated infrastructure.

Secure Protocols: We ensure the use of encrypted communication protocols, such as HTTPS (over TLS), for secure data exchange between our services and external systems. This practice guarantees that data transferred remains protected from interception or tampering, maintaining confidentiality and integrity. For example, when crawlers need to connect to the URL Frontier service, we implement HTTPS to encrypt the communication, ensuring that sensitive data remains secure throughout the transfer process.

Authentication Tokens: Utilizing authentication tokens significantly reduces the risk of unauthorized access, ensuring that only verified users can interact with the system. This method offers an added layer of security beyond traditional password-based authentication. As previously detailed in Section 7.2, we integrate iRODS with the OpenID authentication plugin to implement secure, JWT (JSON Web Token)-based authentication. This integration ensures that each user's identity is validated through a token exchange process, making it harder for unauthorized entities to

gain access. By using this approach, we enhance security, providing robust access control that is more resilient to breaches compared to simple password mechanisms.

8.2 Network and Port Configuration

Port Management: We identify and configure only the specific ports necessary for communication with all of our services depicted in Figure 1 to reduce the system's exposure to potential vulnerabilities. This involves ensuring that all unnecessary ports remain closed, thereby minimizing the risk of unauthorized access. For example, if the Crawlers requires communication with the external service like the URL Frontier service, and it operates over port 8080 for HTTP or 8443 for HTTPS, we make sure that only these specific ports are open.

Local Firewall Configuration: We configure the local firewall on the device hosting the service at each data centre to permit outbound traffic through the required ports. This configuration ensures that only authorized outbound connections are established from the service to external systems. For instance, when the crawlers connect to the Frontier service, the local firewall is set to allow traffic through the necessary ports to the specific IP addresses associated with the Frontier infrastructure, facilitating secure and controlled communication between the crawlers and the Frontier service.

Perimeter Firewall Configuration: We configure the perimeter firewall or edge router at each of our data centre to allow incoming and outgoing traffic only on the specified ports required by our services. This is done in tandem with each of our data centre's security teams. As previously mentioned in the IP Whitelisting part of Section 8.1, we restrict access to known and trusted IP ranges to enhance security. For example, when allowing communication for crawlers that need to access an external service like the URL Frontier service, we ensure that the firewall rules are set to permit traffic only on the designated ports and restrict access to the specific IP ranges associated with the crawlers' network. This approach ensures that only authorized traffic can pass through, maintaining a secure perimeter around each of our partner site's infrastructure.

8.3 Regular Security Audits and Reviews

To ensure the ongoing security and integrity of our infrastructure, we have established a dedicated security working group. This group meets regularly, once a fortnight, to conduct comprehensive discussions of our security practices. The following are some key actions taken as part of our security maintenance:

Firewall Rule Reviews: We regularly audit firewall configurations to ensure that only the necessary ports are open and that no unauthorized changes have been made. We close any ports that are no longer needed to reduce the attack surface.

Security Patching: We ensure that all firewall devices, routers, and software involved in connecting to each of our infrastructure sites are up-to-date with the latest security patches to prevent exploitation of known vulnerabilities.

Intrusion Detection and Monitoring:

While a fully integrated intrusion detection and monitoring system is currently beyond our scope, we look forward to exploring this further with the support of our new third-party partners. As a positive step, we have already implemented some level of intrusion detection on local machines; for instance, at the data centre hosting the Frontier Service, IDS (Intrusion Detection System) packages are installed to monitor and alert on suspicious activities and unauthorized access attempts. These packages provide essential monitoring capabilities on a local scale, and we are

excited about the possibility of expanding and integrating a more comprehensive system across our infrastructure in collaboration with our partners.

8.4 Instructions for Third-Party Partners on Incident Reporting and Response

To ensure responsible and efficient operation of our crawling system, third-party partners can follow these guidelines for incident reporting and handling:

Establish Clear Communication Channels:

- Partners can connect to agreed-upon communication tools (e.g., Mattermost, email lists) to stay informed about the crawling system's activities and potential issues.
- Regularly monitor these channels to stay updated on any incidents or reports related to crawling activities.

Reporting Incidents:

- If partners encounter or receive reports of the crawling system displaying unexpected or potentially harmful behaviour, such as causing Denial-of-Service on web servers or accessing protected content, they should promptly report the incident through the established communication channels.
- Partners can also guide webmasters to report incidents directly via our designated email address (owler@ows.eu), which is provided in the User-Agent string of our crawler's HTTP requests.

Handling Urgent Situations:

- Partners should identify members of their team who are authorized and capable of acting immediately (pressing the "red button") to halt crawling activities if reports indicate serious misconduct. These individuals should be well-informed of their responsibilities and have the necessary access to stop the system.

Responding to Webmaster Complaints:

- If partners receive direct contact from a webmaster, they can inform them that our crawler can be excluded using the robots.txt file.
- All complaints or concerns received should be communicated back to the development team for investigation and resolution.

Monitoring Third-Party Platforms:

- Partners can keep track of popular web platforms where third parties might anonymously share incidents related to web bot misconduct, particularly regarding User-Agents or IP addresses linked to our system.

Documentation and Learning:

- Partners should document all reported incidents, actions taken, and outcomes to contribute to system improvements and ensure transparency in how incidents are managed.

8.5 Instructions for Third-Party Partners on URL Filtering and Blacklisting

URL filtering and tagging are essential for ensuring a secure crawling process within the URL Frontier software. Partners should implement the following measures if the URL Frontier component is hosted on their premises. It is recommended to consult D1.2 for further details on this mechanism.

Using Blacklist Sources:

- Integrate the *Ultimate Hosts Blacklist*⁴⁵ and the blacklists from Université Toulouse Capitole⁴⁶, as these sources are currently used to identify and block harmful URLs. Regularly update these lists via cron jobs to maintain effective filtering.

8.6 Take-down requests

We have implemented the OWLer Dashboard as introduced in Section 2.3 as a key interaction point between webmasters and web data collectors to manage take-down requests efficiently. Third-party partners should be aware of the following guidelines for handling such requests:

Submitting Take-down Requests:

- Webmasters or users can submit requests to remove specific URLs from the Open Web Index directly through the OWLer Dashboard or via email. This provides a straightforward method for reporting content that should be removed.

Providing Justification:

- Users submitting take-down requests are required to provide additional information or justification for their request. This ensures that the removal process adheres to legal, ethical, and compliance standards.

⁴⁵ <https://github.com/Ultimate-Hosts-Blacklist/Ultimate.Hosts.Blacklist>

⁴⁶ <https://dsi.ut-capitole.fr/blacklists/>

9. Conclusion

This document has provided a comprehensive overview of the OpenWebSearch Federated Data Infrastructure (OWS-FDI), covering its architecture, integration processes, technical workflows, and security measures essential for successfully onboarding and collaborating with third-party infrastructure partners. We have detailed how the crawling, preprocessing, and indexing pipelines function within the OWS-FDI, explained the integration with the LEXIS platform, and elaborated on the roles of various interfaces, logging, and monitoring services.

The OWS Data Distribution Layer (OWS-DDL) and the mechanisms for data federation and authentication were presented to ensure partners understand how data is managed and shared. Furthermore, we have emphasized the importance of security practices, such as authentication controls, network configurations, and regular audits, to maintain a robust infrastructure. We also outlined our approach to incident reporting, takedown requests, and the transparent use of downstream data, demonstrating our commitment to legal, ethical, and transparent practices.

As we move forward, our focus will be on continuously improving and expanding the OWS-FDI to support collaboration, scalability, and adaptability, ensuring it remains a secure, efficient, and valuable platform for all partners involved. We look forward to ongoing partnerships and contributions that will further enhance the OWS infrastructure. By the start of August 2024, the project has indexed approximately 10.7 billion web pages in 184 languages, resulting in the crawling of ca. 300 TiB of web data.

Going forward in the project's timeline, the infrastructure partners will focus on improving and expanding the current documentation and training material in conjecture with the newly onboarded partners and also scaling the pilot OWS-FDI. In summary, this documentation aligns with the ethical guidelines set by Ethical, Legal, and Societal Aspects, work package ensuring transparency and compliance. It also strengthens the project's sustainability by establishing a valuable resource that supports future onboarding and long-term project goals.

Appendix

A.1 Overview of open-source software outputs

Each of the parts that the partners have collaboratively developed to build and sustain the OWI is published as an open-source software project. Figure 11 lists all of these projects and includes links to their respective Git repositories, as well as a version archived on Zenodo near the end of the first year.

Table 2: Open-source software packages developed to build and use the OWI

Id	01
Title	iRODS installation
Documentation	https://docs.irods.org/4.2.12/getting_started/installation/

Id	02
Title	iRODS federation
Documentaiton	https://docs.irods.org/4.2.12/system_overview/federation/

Id	03
Title	Owilix: a command line tool for access to the OWI
Repository	https://opencode.it4i.eu/openwebsearcheu-public/owi-cli
Archived	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13833664

Id	04
Title	Open Web Search Crawler (OWLer) StormCrawler (see also D1.1)
Repository	https://opencode.it4i.eu/openwebsearcheu-public/owlr
Archived	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8278932

Id	05
Title	Open Web Search Crawler (OWLer) URLFrontier (see also D1.1)
Repository	https://opencode.it4i.eu/openwebsearcheu-public/urlfrontier
Archived	https://zenodo.org/records/13836904

Id	06
Title	Resiliparse: WARC/HTML parsing and preprocessing library
Repository	https://github.com/chatnoir-eu/chatnoir-resiliparse

Archived	https://zenodo.org/records/13739396
-----------------	---

Id	07
Title	Resilipipe: Preprocessing at scale
Repository	https://opencode.it4i.eu/openwebsearcheu-public/preprocessing-pipeline
Archived	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13784624

Id	08
Title	TIRA: platform for replicability and comparison of information retrieval experiments
Repository	https://github.com/tira-io/tira
Archived	https://zenodo.org/records/13739358

Id	09
Title	Open Web Search Indexer
Repository	https://opencode.it4i.eu/openwebsearcheu-public/spark-indexer
Archived	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8261098

Id	10
Title	Spark deployment framework
Repository	https://opencode.it4i.eu/openwebsearcheu-public/spark-deployment
Archived	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13693137

Id	11
Title	CIFF toolkit: library for processing WARC files
Repository	https://opencode.it4i.eu/openwebsearcheu-public/ciff-toolkit/
Archived	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13693064

Id	12
Title	CIFF to Lucene index converter
Repository	https://github.com/informagi/lucene-ciff
Archived	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13710610

Id	13
Title	MOSAIC2go Configuration Tool
Repository	https://opencode.it4i.eu/openwebsearcheu/wp4/mosaic2go-configuration-service https://opencode.it4i.eu/openwebsearcheu/wp4/mosaic2go-web-frontend (private and password protected repositories)
Archived	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13800054

A.2 List of Acronyms/Abbreviations also in context of all deliverables mentioned in this document

Table 3: List of Abbreviations/Acronyms

Acronym/Abbreviation	Term
AAI	Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure
ABAC	Attribute-Based Access Control
API	Application Programming Interface
CIFF	Common Index File Format
CPU	Central Processing Unit
DAG	Directed Acyclic Graph
DDL	Data Distribution Layer
FDI	Federated Data Infrastructure
FTP	File Transfer Protocol
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HDD	Hard Disk Drive
HPC	High-Performance Computing
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
HTTPS	HTTP Secure
HTML	HyperText Markup Language
IAM	Identity and Access Management
IdP	Identity Provider
IaaS	Infrastructure as a Service
ISO 27001	International Organization for Standardization 27001
JWT	JSON Web Token
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
LLM	Large Language Model
LV	Logical Volume
NGI	Next Generation Internet
OIDC	OpenID Connect
OWI	Open Web Index

OWS	Open Web Search
OWS-FDI	Open Web Services - Federated Data Infrastructure
POSIX	Portable Operating System Interface
RAM	Random-Access Memory
RBAC	Role-Based Access Control
REST	REpresentational State Transfer
S3	Simple Storage Service
SQL	Structured Query Language
SSD	Solid State Drive
SSL	Secure Sockets Layer
SSO	Single Sign-On
TCP/IP	Transmission Control Protocol/Internet Protocol
TLS	Transport Layer Security
UI	User Interface
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
UUID	Universally Unique Identifier
VM	Virtual Machine
WARC	Web ARChive
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium
WP	Work Package
WP1	Work Package 1
WP2	Work Package 2
WP3	Work Package 3
WP5	Work Package 5
WP6	Work Package 6
Y1	Year 1
Y2	Year 2

A.3 Glossary

Table 4: List of Concepts, Technology/Framework/Tools/Application

Term	Description
Apache Spark	An open-source distributed general-purpose cluster-computing framework.
Apache Parquet	A columnar storage file format, part of the Apache Hadoop ecosystem.
Apache Storm	A platform for distributed stream processing.
Authentication	A system that manages user permissions for various services.
Authorization	A system that manages user access for various services.
EUDAT B2ACCESS	A service for storing research data securely in the European Data Infrastructure.
Compute Infrastructure	The collection of hardware resources like servers and storage devices that power computing tasks.
Compute Workflow Orchestration Engine	A system within the LEXIS framework that coordinates and manages high-performance computing workflows and jobs.
Crawling, Crawler	The automated process by which a web crawler or spider systematically browses the internet, typically for the purpose of indexing web pages or gathering data.
crawling=>pre-processing=>indexing pipeline	A sequential process in data handling where 'crawling' involves systematically browsing the web to gather data, 'pre-processing' entails preparing and refining this data, and 'indexing' involves organizing the data to facilitate efficient retrieval and analysis.
Crawling Queue	A component in web crawling that manages and prioritizes the sequence of web pages to be crawled.
Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG)	A mathematical structure consisting of nodes connected by directed edges, where no cycles are formed, commonly used to represent workflows or dependencies in computer science.
Frontiers Apps	Applications that manage the crawling queue and control web crawling activities.
High Performance Computing (HPC)	Very powerful computers used for solving complex problems.
iRODS	Integrated Rule-Oriented Data System for managing distributed data.
iRODS zone	Basic iRODS deployment is a so-called zone, which has its own set of users and a storage assigned on a local storage array. Each zone maintains its own tree of datasets/collections, their metadata and enforces its access rules.

JSON Web Tokens (JWT)	A secure way to send information between two parties on the internet in a format that's easy to read and verify.
Large Language Model (LLM)	An advanced artificial intelligence system capable of understanding and generating human-like text across various languages and domains, trained on vast amounts of textual data.
LEXIS	Access to High-Performance Computing and cloud-computing infrastructures.
Metadata	Data that provides information about other data, often used to describe the content, quality, condition, origin, and other characteristics of data, especially in the context of large-scale web data collection and analysis.
OWS Data Distribution Layer (OWS-DDL)	A layer in the OWS system for managing data storage and distribution across multiple sites.
Pipeline	In the context of the Open Web Index (OWI), a pipeline refers to a sequence of data processing steps or stages arranged in a linear workflow for the systematic collection, processing, and indexing of web data.
Platform	In the context of OWS-FDI, a platform refers to a foundational technology or environment that supports and facilitates the integration and operation of various applications, frameworks, and tools in distributed computing and storage.
plugins	Software components that add specific features or functionalities to an existing computer program, allowing for customization and enhancement of the program's capabilities, particularly in content analysis and data processing applications.
Pre-processing	A crucial step in the data pipeline involving the preparation and transformation of raw data, such as web content, into a format suitable for further analysis and processing, like indexing.
Py4lexis API	An API used for downloading bulk data within the OWS ecosystem.
Resiliparse	A software tool for parsing and cleaning HTML content.
S3	A scalable storage service that offers object storage widely used for storing and retrieving large amounts of data over the internet.
StormCrawler	A scalable web crawling framework, designed to be used with Apache Storm.
TIRA Platform	A platform for hosting and managing research software, particularly in the fields of information retrieval and natural language processing.
URLFrontier	Open Source project for managing web crawling queues.
Virtual machines	Software-based emulations of physical computers that provide the functionality of a physical computer, enabling multiple operating

	systems and applications to run on a single physical machine, often used in cloud computing for efficient resource management and task distribution.
WARC Files	Web ARChive files, a file format used to store "harvested" web content, including HTML, images, and other media from web crawls.